

CROP AND RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Fertilizer management—inorganic

Phosphorus effects on rice yield under different moisture regimes during wet season in West Bengal, India

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We conducted a field trial from 1986 to 1988 to study how P affected rice yield during wet season under different moisture regimes at a seed farm in Memari, Burdwan, in the Gangetic alluvial plains of West Bengal.

Soil is silt loam with pH 6.8, 0.9% organic C, CEC 15 meq/100 g soil, 73 kg available P/ha, and 21 6 kg exchangeable K/ha in the top 15 cm of soil.

The experiment was laid out in a random block design, replicated three times. P was applied as single

superphosphate (16% water soluble and 2% citric soluble P₂O₅) at 0, 30, 60, and 90 kg P/ha under three moisture regimes (see table). The crop received the recommended 80 kg N/ha and 41 kg K/ha and 48, 67, and 60 cm of rain during the growth periods in respective years. Irrigation was supplied as per treatment. IR36 raised in wetbed (60 kg seed/ha) was transplanted 30 d after seeding at 25 × 25-cm spacing with 2 plants/hill.

P up to 26 kg/ha significantly increased grain yield regardless of irrigation regime (see table). Grain yield was greater with continuous flooding at all P levels; however, grain yield/unit water input increased by 60% in the I₂ treatment compared with the continuous flooding. These results suggest that P fertilizer and irrigation water are substitutive inputs with regard to their interactive effects on yield. For example, total water input decreased by more than 40% from treatment I₀ to I₂ based on comparison of the pooled means. In

contrast, the I₀ treatment without P inputs and the I₂ treatment with 13 kg P/ha had equivalent grain yields of 4.5 t/ha.

Applying P can help stabilize yields on P-deficient soil when irrigation water is limited. □

Fertilizer management—organic

Intercropping green manure (GM) crops with dry season irrigated rice

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Legume crops can restore soil fertility that is depleted because of continuous cropping. But GM crops are rarely used in rainfed wetland rice-based cropping systems. *Sesbania aculeata* is sometimes intercropped with dry seeded or wet seeded rainfed lowland rice and *S. rostrata* can grow under flooded conditions. In trials during the 1991 dry season, we evaluated the effect of GM crops on dry season irrigated rice at varied planting dates and the subsequent use of this biomass for succeeding rice production.

Forty-day-old seedlings of BR14 were transplanted 29 Jan 1991 at 20 × 20-cm spacing. *S. aculeata* and *S. rostrata* were

Table 1. Yield of rice and GM sown on 4 dates (10, 20, 40, 60 DT) as affected by intercropping, 1991 dry season.

GM crop	Grain yield (t/ha)				GM biomass ^a (t/ha)			
	10	20	40	60	10	20	40	
<i>S. aculeata</i>	2.6	3.4	4.7	4.6	3.9	3.3	0.7	
<i>S. rostrata</i>	3.3	3.3	4.7	4.3	6.9	5.7	0.7	
Control	4.5	4.4	4.9	4.6	-	-	-	
SE	0.1				0.1			

^aAt 60 DT seed germination failed. GM crops were harvested on 25 May 1991.

P level effects on IR36 yield under 3 moisture regimes during rainy season in Indo-Gangetic Plains, West Bengal, India.

Year	Moisture regime ^a	Grain yield (t/ha)					Total water use ^b (cm)	Water use efficiency (kg/ha per cm)	
		0 kg P/ha	13 kg P/ha	26 kg P/ha	37 kg P/ha	Mean		0 kg P/ha	26 kg P/ha
1986	I ₀	4.1	4.6	5.0	5.1	4.7	88	46.6	56.8
	I ₁	4.0	4.5	4.8	4.8	4.5	55	72.7	87.3
	I ₂	3.9	4.4	4.7	4.9	4.5	45	86.7	104.4
	Mean	4.0	4.5	4.8	5.0				
1987	I ₀	4.7	5.2	5.5	5.7	5.3	99	47.5	55.6
	I ₁	4.3	4.6	5.0	5.1	4.7	67	64.2	74.6
	I ₂	4.0	4.4	4.7	4.7	4.4	52	76.9	90.4
	Mean	4.3	4.7	5.1	5.2				
1988	I ₀	4.8	5.3	5.7	5.7	5.3	90	53.3	63.3
	I ₁	4.5	4.9	5.2	5.3	5.0	65	69.2	80.0
	I ₂	4.3	4.7	5.2	5.2	4.9	58	74.1	89.7
	Mean	4.5	5.0	5.3	5.4				
Pooled	I ₀	4.5	5.0	5.4	5.5	5.1	92	48.9	58.7
	I ₁	4.2	4.7	5.0	5.1	4.7	62	67.7	80.6
	I ₂	4.0	4.5	4.9	4.9	4.6	52	76.9	94.2
	Mean	4.3	4.7	5.1	5.2				
LSD(0.05)	1986	1987	1988	Pooled					
P level	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.1					
Moisture regime	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1					

^aI₀= continuous submergence of 5 ± 2 cm irrigation water, I₁= 5 ± 2 cm irrigation water 5 d after impounded water disappeared, and I₂= 5 ± 2 cm irrigation water 10 d after impounded water disappeared. Total water use = irrigation water applied (cm) plus rainfall (cm).